

PROGESTERONE LEVELS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF VOMITING DURING PREGNANCY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14706694>

Abstract. *The obtained data indicates ambiguous progesterone content in the blood serum of patients with pregnancy vomiting, both mild and severe. Low gestogen levels were found in 75.0% of pregnant women with mild vomiting and in 43.5% with severe vomiting.*

The aim is to determine the level of progesterone in the blood serum of women with pregnancy vomiting and to assess its role in the development of the pathological process. The study was conducted at the Fergana Regional Perinatal Center with 39 pregnant women experiencing vomiting. The patients were divided into three groups: Group 1: 16 patients with mild vomiting, Group 2: 23 patients with severe vomiting. The control group consisted of 12 apparently healthy pregnant women without signs of toxicosis. Progesterone levels in the control group were 30.4 ± 2.1 ng/ml. 2. Group 1: Progesterone levels in 75% of patients were 6.0 ± 0.7 ng/ml ($p < 0.0001$). In 25% of patients, the level was close to the upper limit of the normal range - 66.1 ± 3.5 ng/ml.

Group 2: Progesterone levels were 6.5 ± 1.0 ng/ml ($p < 0.0001$) in 43.5% of patients.

In 56.5%, the level was significantly higher - 67.0 ± 3.3 ng/ml. The obtained data indicate an ambiguous content of progesterone in the blood serum of patients with vomiting during pregnancy, both mild and severe. Low gestogen levels were found in 75.0% of pregnant women with mild vomiting and 43.5% with severe vomiting. It is recommended for patients with vomiting during pregnancy to determine the content of progesterone in the blood to predict and prevent unfavorable pregnancy outcomes.

Keywords: *vomiting syndrome, pregnancy toxicosis, progesterone, pregnancy pathologies.*

Relevance. In obstetric practice, among the early toxicosis of pregnant women, vomiting of pregnancy (VP) is the most common. According to various authors, the frequency of this pregnancy complication ranges from 40% to 70% [13,14]. According to ACOG and other researchers, "50-80% of pregnant patients complain of nausea, and in 50% of cases, nausea is accompanied by repeated vomiting" [16,23]. Nausea and vomiting usually begin at 4-5 weeks of pregnancy and end by 10-12 weeks. Among the population, there is a common opinion that morning sickness is an early sign of pregnancy and does not require treatment, as it will pass by 3 months. According to literature, in 35% of pregnant women, VP, although not leading to hospitalization, significantly worsens their quality of life, work capacity, and family relationships [3]. In addition, mild vomiting in 1.5-2% of pregnant women can progress to severe - hyperemesis gravidarum, accompanied by dehydration, nutrition and metabolism disorders [2,9,10], hypochloremic alkalosis with electrolyte disturbances, up to liver damage, polyneuropathy, encephalopathy, etc. [7], and can lead to muscle spasms and ketonuria [20]. M.S. Fejzo et al. report that hyperemesis gravidarum accounts for 0.3-10.8% [19]. In rare cases, it can lead to maternal mortality [17].

Regarding the causes of VP development, O.A. Kutuzova [6] notes that "first-trimester toxicosis is an early manifestation of gestational maladaptation." There are many theories in the

literature, in particular, hormonal, neurogenic, immunological, cortico-visceral, and reflex, but according to E.K. Aylamazyan [1], several causes may be simultaneously involved in the pathogenesis of toxicosis development.

VP negatively affects the outcome of pregnancy and childbirth. Complications can affect the woman, the fetus, or both, and can develop at different stages of pregnancy. The balance of electrolytes needed to maintain normal body functioning is disrupted. Severe liver damage may develop, leading to jaundice and destruction of liver tissue. Several serious complications are distinguished, such as esophageal rupture, retinal hemorrhages, pneumothorax, kidney damage, and Wernicke's encephalopathy [24]. In pregnant women who experience vomiting in the second trimester, preeclampsia is observed 2 times more often, and the risk of placental abruption increases 3-fold [8,4]. V. Keskinliç in his article mentions that hyperemesis gravidarum is identified as a transitory risk factor for pulmonary embolism (PE) [18, 22, 25, 21]. E.Yu. Yupatov, A.V. Filyushina [15] and other authors [18,22,25] note that vomiting in pregnancy often contributes to the development of complications in patients during the second trimester and later gestation periods, such as preterm labor, preeclampsia, placental insufficiency, fetal growth restriction, and cases of placental abruption. Additionally, newborns are more likely to be at risk for perinatal pathology - hypotrophy, central nervous system damage (predominantly of hypoxic-ischemic origin), neonatal asphyxia, etc. [7]. Other observations have demonstrated an increase in the number of low-birth-weight infants [18,22,25]. Complications in the first half of pregnancy mirror deeper and pregnancy-specific disturbances at the stage of first-wave cytotrophoblast invasion and serve as predictors of severe gestational complications in the second half of pregnancy (placental insufficiency, preterm labor, preeclampsia, etc.) [11,13,14].

All of the above testifies to the relevance of the topic under study and determined the choice of the goal.

Goal: To study the risk factors for the development of vomiting in pregnant women in Ferghana region.

Material and methods: 39 women with VP admitted to the Fergana Regional Perinatal Center were examined. Pregnant women with VP were divided into two groups: the first group consisted of 16 patients with mild vomiting, the second group consisted of 23 patients with severe vomiting. The control group comprised 12 practically healthy pregnant women without signs of toxicosis. All examined pregnant women had a gestational age ranging from 6 to 10 weeks. The pregnant women in the main and control groups were identical in age, parity, and gestational age ($p>0.05$). Progesterone (PR) levels in the blood of pregnant women were determined using the ELISA method with a "Human" reagent (Germany), with normal values in the first trimester ranging from 11.4-76.3 ng/ml. The obtained results were processed using the method of variational statistics with the determination of $M\pm m$, Student t-test, and the degree of significance p .

The severity of vomiting in pregnant women was assessed according to G.M. Savelyeva [12] (Table 1).

Results and discussion. It was established that the PR level in the blood of pregnant women in the control group was 30.4 ± 2.1 ng/ml. In the 1st group, 75% (12) of pregnant women had a PR level of 6.0 ± 0.7 (1.5-6.3) ng/ml, which was significantly 5 times lower than the control group ($P<0.0001$). In the remaining 25% (4) of pregnant women in this group, PR was at the upper limit of the normal range - 66.1 ± 3.5 (60.9-73.4) ng/ml. In 43.5% (10) of pregnant women with severe vomiting, the PR level was 6.5 ± 1.0 (1.2-9.1) ng/ml, which was significantly 4.7 times lower than

the control value ($P < 0.0001$). In the remaining 56.5% (13) of pregnant women in this group, PR was at the upper limit of the normal range - 67.0 ± 3.3 (52.9-88.1) ng/ml and was significantly 2.2 times higher than the control group ($P < 0.0001$).

Symptoms	Severity level		
	Easy	Average	Heavy
Vomiting frequency, times per day	From 3 to 5	From 6 to 10	From 11 and above
HR	80-90	90-100	Over 100
SBP, mm Hg	110-120	100-110	Below 100
Weekly weight loss from initial weight	Up to 5%	Up to 6-10%	Over 10%
Low-grade fever	No	Rarely	Frequently
Yellowing of sclera and skin	No	5-7%	20-30%
Hyperbilirubinemia, $\mu\text{mol/L}$	No	21-40	21-60
Dry skin	+	++	+++
Stool	Every day	Once every 3 days	Delay > 3 days
Urine output, ml	900-800	800-700	Less than 700
Ketonuria	+, ++	+, +++ (periodically in 20-50% of cases)	+++, ++++ (periodically at 70-100%)

A decreased PR level in the blood indicates a high risk of preterm birth and the need for replacement therapy. Considering that PR has an immunosuppressive effect, it should be noted that its deficiency may promote an aggressive maternal response to fetal antigens, which can clinically manifest as progression of early toxicosis or pregnancy termination. The results of the study allow us to conclude that PR administration in RB requires an individualized approach, based on the detection of its low level in the blood.

Diagram 1. Age composition of pregnant women with vomiting by group

The parity by group is shown in Diagram 2.

The first pregnancy was observed in 37.4% (46) of women, the second in 27.6% (34), and the third or more in 35.0% (43), meaning that repeat pregnancies predominated at 62.6% (67). However, it should be noted that among pregnant women with mild vomiting, first-time pregnancies accounted for 46.4%, while in moderate pregnancy vomiting they constituted 1/3, and in severe pregnancy vomiting - 1/4.

The hospitalization periods of pregnant women with vomiting by group are presented in Diagram 2.

One-third (33.3%) of pregnant women were admitted to the hospital at 4-6 weeks of gestation, another third (31.7%) - at 7-8 weeks, 21.6% (26) - at 9-12 weeks, and 13.8% (17) - at 12 weeks or later. Of these, 32.1% of pregnant women in group 1 were admitted to the hospital at 9-12 weeks, 48.9% in group 2 - at 4-6 weeks, and 50.0% in group 3 - mainly at 7-8 weeks of gestation.

From the obstetric history, it was established that 40.7% (50) of women had given birth, 23.6% (28) had undergone abortions, of which 55.2% (16) were due to non-developing pregnancies. Indication for pregnancy termination due to medical reasons - uncontrollable vomiting - was present in 1 case (0.8%).

Conclusions. The obtained data indicate ambiguous progesterone levels in the blood serum of patients with pregnancy vomiting, both mild and severe. Low gestogen levels were found in 75.0% of pregnant women with mild vomiting and 43.5% with severe vomiting. It is recommended that patients with pregnancy vomiting have their blood progesterone levels determined to predict and prevent unfavorable pregnancy outcomes.

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